

The effect of the FDI to digital readiness: Working paper

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Abstract:

Paper deals with the role of the foreign direct investment in improving technology and digitalization in central and southeast European countries. Frontier technology readiness index is the variable, the investment would affect by increasing its score. Apart from the foreign direct investment, 12 variables are used to in panel regression analysis. The variables represent different areas as the performance of the economy, international trade, labour, education, research and digital infrastructure. The data used consist of 17 cross-sectional units – countries from central and southeast Europe and 12 time series – period 2008-2019 for which is the Index available. Result indicates that the foreign direct investment inflow has positive and statistically significant effect on the score of the Index. It means that the higher the FDI inflows to a country, the higher score in the Index is achieved. In other words. Foreign direct investment might be considered as the factor enhancing the digitalization, technology improvement and country readiness to use, adopt or adapt advanced technologies. The result confirms the technological spill-over effect of foreign direct investment to host economy.

Key words: digitalization, Readiness for Frontier Technology Index, foreign direct investment, central and southeast Europe

JEL Classification: F21, O33, O52

Acknowledgement

The paper is the result of implementation of the project “Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia”, acronym: ODDEA, project ID: 101086381, co-funded by the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Introduction

The current development shows the necessity for digital transformation meaning shift to digital environment and the adopting of advanced technologies. Is clear that countries that already launched this process have comparative advantage when comparing the countries that are lagging behind in use of technologies and digitalization. The state of the digitalization and technological level differs also

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within European countries, even those in the same region. One of the factors that would affect the technological progress and the digitalization in a country is the foreign direct investment inflow. FDI inflow positive impact are investigated by many researchers. One of the positive impacts commonly found in FDI analysis is technological spill-over effect that is considered as the improvement of the technologies and enhancing digital progress in host economies. The higher the FDI inflow to a host economy, the better technologies would be implemented and country would achieve higher technological level and digitalization. To measure the country readiness to launched, adopt and adapt advanced technologies, United Nation Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) has established the Readiness for Frontier Technology Index (RFTI) that has several sub-indexes and is created by considering several indicators. The RFTI measure, how is a country prepared to adopt new technologies considering variables as internet users, internet speed, speed, years of schooling, high skill employment, publications, patents, high tech export, digitally deliverable services export or access to finance by domestic credit to private sector. With this regard, we would assume that the FDI inflow has positive impact on the RFTI, which would represent the level of the technology and digitalization in a host county or investment. Surely, the Index is not able to capture all aspects of digitalization and technologies, but it is a very good parameter that is available for all analysed countries using the same measurement methodology avoiding difference in methods to measure or evaluate technological level and digitalization in different countries.

The paper is organized as follows. First part provides the literature review of the digitalization, technological progress and development and the role of the foreign direct investment. Second part deals with the methodology of the paper and data description. The most important part – results and discussion deal with the output of the analysis. The last part summarizes the main findings of the paper.

Literature review

The research on the Foreign direct investment is extensive and the area is well investigated. Foreign direct investment has often crucial role in the transformation process of economies, including the adopting new and advanced technologies that were not used formerly in host countries of investments. The technology spill-overs resulting in the economic growth are evident and proved by many authors (e.g. Asongu and Odhiambo, 2020; Borensztein, De Gregorio and Lee, 1998; Blomström and Kokko, 1997 and 2002; Combes, Kinda, Ouedraogo and Plane, 2019; Dimelis and Louri, 2004; Gherigi and Voytovych, 2018; Javorcik, 2004; Khan, Asteriou and Jefferies, 2023 or Sadik and Bolbol, 2001). The feature of the FDI has changed over the past years. Sure, there are still market seeking, resource seeking and efficiency seeking FDI, but in the current digital environment, we might also claim to be arisen technology-seeking investment. The study by Kim and Choi (2020) indicates that there is a curvilinear relationship between FDI inflow and technological capability of the host country. FDI is especially high when host country host countries have extremely high technological capability or extremely low technological capability (Kim and Choi, 2020, p. 13). Such result is different as commonly assumed linear relations between the FDI and technological level was assumed. However, the result might be affected by the motives of investors. If investments are resource or efficiency-seeking and technologies are imported to the country, there is not necessity to have well developed technological capacity or infrastructure. Otherwise, if investments are technology-seeking or knowledge-seeking, the technological capacity is required.

The foreign direct investment might be driving force to enhance and support digitalization process in host economies by launching new technologies and decline the digital divide between home and host countries. However, the promoting agencies and government must be willing to provide conditions

allowing those investments flowing into a country and be helpful in building adequate infrastructure. Attracting more foreign direct investment into the digital economy will not only be a key strategy in economic recovery from pandemic, but it will also be a key strategy in building the digital infrastructure, digital entrepreneurship, and digital literacy so vital for success in the new digital world (Satyanand, 2021, p. 5). The world is characterized by a clear distance between hyper-digitalized and under-connected economies (Nguyen, V.B., 2023, p. 2). The divide is significant in some sectors, such as frontier technologies and digital data (Nguyen, V.B., 2023, p. 2). The digital economy benefits firms in both developed and emerging markets – as long as the country has a strong ICT infrastructure (Eden, 2016, p. 6). Foreign direct investment will not flow to host countries with weak telecommunication infrastructure even the other determinants might be advantageous. The frontier technologies necessary to be adopting include automation and robotics, internet of things, 3D manufacturing, cloud computing, blockchain or artificial intelligence. Ha and Huyen (2022) found that that digitalization plays a critical role in promoting FDI inflows in both short term and long term (Ha and Huyen, 2022, p.1). They have used the feasible least square estimation for 23 European countries for two periods relating to the pandemic – 2015-2019 and for 2020. In a policy brief for the Western Balkan, Mrdović (Mrdović, 2023) stated that international players have helped to advance digital infrastructure, promote digital skills, and assist in the execution of digitalisation programmes. This was not only by the financial support, but also by technical know-how and knowledge exchange. Creating a digital-friendly investment climate may require specific policies, regulations and measures (Eden, 2016, p. 16). Such environment would increase country digital competences and attract more FDI in the digital economy associated with other FDI benefits. FDI brings not only a capital, but also knowledge, and technology what increases the digital capacities of host county of investment (Eden, 2016, p. 1). The role of the FDI in improving digitalization in very important. As noted by the UNCTAD, one way to grow the digital economy and increase digital competitiveness is through attracting FDI. The digital economy has important implications for investment, and investment is crucial for digital development (UNCTAD, 2017, p. 158). The relation between the FDI and digitalization is mutual. The FDI inflows the requires some satisfactory level of digital infrastructure and at the same time, the digitalization is being improved by foreign investments.

Despite the possibilities of interconnection that technological and digital advances allow, the digital transformation has not spread uniformly throughout the world, nor has it caused the same effects in all countries equally, as some have benefited more than others (Parra – Pérez-Pons – González, 2012, p. 182). The adoption of advanced technologies and digitalization is the factor affecting the performance of economies. Parra, Pérez-Pons and González (2012) found that Digital Adoption Index is significant variable affecting the economic growth (Parra, Pérez-Pons and González, 2012, p.187). They analysed the group of 176 countries for two periods – 2014 and 2016 by the use of the GMM estimation method. Authors provide estimation for the overall sample and then differently for Europe, Asia, Americas and Africa. When analysing Africa and Americas, the Digital Adoption Index resulted to be non-significant. Zhang, Zhao, Cheng, Li, Wang, Yang and Tian (2022) also examined the relations between the digital economy and the economic growth for “Belt and Road” countries that consists of 31 countries from Europe and Asia (the list might be found at Zhang, Zhao, Cheng, Li, Wang, Yang and Tian, 2022, p. 7). Firstly, they developed comprehensive evaluation system of digital economy consisting of different categories as digital infrastructure, digital economy openness, digital technology innovation environment and competitiveness (Zhang, Zhao, Cheng, Li, Wang, Yang and Tian, 2022, p. 4). These categories include several indicators that characterize each category. Authors used several variables determining the GDP of a country, including the developed digital economy development score. For this purpose, the panel regression analysis with fixed effect was used. Also, GMM method

was used as well. The digital economy development that was established by authors has been found to have positive and statistically significant impact on the economic growth.

Data and methodology

The literature review and studies by the international organization provides various determinants and factors affecting the level of technologies that are established and enroot in a country. At the same time, literature identifies factors, which might be significant to enhance technological development. For the analysis, we found appropriate to use the Readiness for Frontier Technology Index as the measure of the technologies used in a country and the readiness of a country to use advanced technologies. The index is then considered also as the level of digitalization in a country as it includes indicators relating to the digitalization. The index availability is since 2008 until 2019 and captures 158 countries and is comparable between all countries. For years 2021 and 2023, the Index is available by created rank by countries and the score of the index is only by two decimals, while for years 2008-2019, six decimals were provided and the rank was not done by the UNCTAD. For that reason, we include only 2008-2019 period to the econometric analysis. In addition, the period since 2019 was affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, so we just provide the descriptive analysis of the rank for available years in 2021 and 2022.

The Readiness for Frontier Technology Index was established by the United Nation Conference on Trade and Development. The Index was developed to assess the country readiness for using, adopting and adapting new technologies. It includes 5 sub-indexes, which are ICT deployment, skills, R&D activity, industry activity and access to finance (UNCTAD, Technology and Innovation Report 2021, p. 144). The short description of sub-indexes and indicators used are given in the Table 1. The overall index is calculated by assigning the weights generated by the principal component analysis (PCA) with rotation to the three principal components, and then standardized and normalized within the range of 0 to 1 (UNCTAD, Technology and Innovation Report 2021, p. 147).

Table 1: Description and indicators used in the Frontier technology readiness index

Sub-index	Description	Indicator	Source	No. of countries
ICT deployment	The level of ICT infrastructure. The use and adopting of artificial intelligence, big, data, block-chain and internet technologies. The ICT infrastructure is considered as the quality of infrastructure give presumptions for the use of advanced technologies and their effective use.	Internet users (% of population)	ITU	210
		Mean download speed (Mbps)	M-Lab	194
Skills	Adopting and use of technologies required qualified and skilled people.	Expected years of schooling	UNDP	191

	The index considered two types of skills – practical and formal training and learning by doing.	High-skill employment (% of working population)	ILO	185
R&D activity	R&D activities are needed for adoption and adaption of technologies as those required adjustment and modification for the use in particular country or industry.	Number of scientific publications on frontier technologies	SCOPUS	234
		Number of patents filed on frontier technologies	PatSeer	234
Industry activity	Adaption of frontier technologies in industry related activities. Mostly, technologies are use in high-tech manufacturing, finance and ICT.	High-tech manufacturers exports (% of total merchandise trade)	UNCTAD	216
		Digitally deliverable services exports (% of total service trade)	UNCTAD	186
Access to finance	Better access for funding the private sector to adopt new technologies enhances the technological development.	Domestic credit to private sector (% of GDP)	WB/IMF/OECD	213

Source: UNCTAD, 2021, Technology and Innovation Report 2021, pp. 144-145

The focus of the analysis is bringing the answer if the foreign direct investment inflow to analysed central and southeast European countries have positive impact on the level of digitalization, technologies and the precondition of the use of new or advanced technologies. We assume the positive and statistically significant variable of the foreign direct investment inflow, thus the higher the FDI inflow to a country, the higher RFTI has country achieved. This assumption would also confirm the positive technology spill-over effects of the FDI to a host economy.

The goal of the paper is to identify and assess the role of the foreign direct investment in affecting the technology readiness of central and southeast European countries.

To find the significance of the foreign direct investment in affecting the technology and digitalization representing by the RFTI, we have run the regression model that includes 13 variables. One of the variables is the FDI inflow. Other exogenous variables represent factors that might have effect on the state of the digitalization in a country. These variables are described in Table 2. Variables represent different areas affecting digitalization as the performance of the economy, international trade, labour, education, research or digital infrastructure as well as the international capital flows represented by the inward foreign direct investment. The variables used in the estimation are not included in the RFTI indicators. We consider the RFTI as the expression or measure of the level of the digitalization and technology and digitalization in a country.

We will use the panel data consisting of 17 cross-sectional data – 17 central and southeast European countries within the period of 2008-2019 for which is the RFTI available. Unfortunately, we do not have full sample of data as several various missing observations for particular years or countries. Countries captured in analysis are Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland. Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Albania, Bosna and Hercegovina Croatia, Greece, Montenegro, North Macedonia

and Serbia. The data source is UNCTADstat the statistics of the World Bank – World Development Indicators. All monetary variables are adjusted to constant prices of 2015 base year in USD.

To estimate the role of the FDI in affecting the level of technology and digitalization, we ran panel regression with fixed effects that includes 13 exogenous variables and endogenous variable RFTI. In the centre of our interest is variable foreign direct investment inflow that we consider will have positive and statistically significant impact on the level of technology and digitalization represented by the RFTI.

Table 2: The list of variables used in model

Variable	Description	Measure	Indicator	Source
RFTI _{i,t}	frontier technology readiness index	values 0 – 1	-	UNCTADstat
FDI _{i,t}	foreign direct investment, inflow to host country	mil. USD, constant prices 2015	international capital flows	UNCTADstat
GDP _{i,t}	gross domestic product	mil. USD, constant prices 2015	performance of the economy	UNCTADstat
ICT_SERVICES_EX _{i,t}	international trade in ICT services - export	% of total trade in services	international trade	UNCTADstat
ICT_SERVICES_IM _{i,t}	international trade in ICT services – import	% of total trade in services	international trade	UNCTADstat
ICT_GOODS_EX _{i,t}	international trade in ICT goods - export	% of total trade	international trade	UNCTADstat
ICT_GOODS_IM _{i,t}	international trade in ICT goods – import	% of total trade	international trade	UNCTADstat
GFCF _{i,t}	gross fixed capital formation	mil. USD, constant prices 2015		UNCTADstat
EPR _{i,t}	employment to population ration	% of population, 15+	labour	World Bank - World Development Indicators
UN _{i,t}	unemployment rate	% of labour force	social conditions	World Bank - World Development Indicators
ENROL _{i,t}	tertiary school enrolment	% of gross	education	World Bank - World Development Indicators
RD _{i,t}	expenditure on research and development	% of GDP	research	World Bank - World Development Indicators
RES _{i,t}	researchers in R&D	per million people	research	World Bank - World Development Indicators
SERVER _{i,t}	secure internet servers	per 1 million people	digital infrastructure	World Bank - World Development Indicators

PHONE _{i,t}	mobile cellular subscriptions	per 100 people	digital infrastructure	World Bank - World Development Indicators
BROADBAND _{i,t}	fixed broadband subscriptions	per 100 people	digital infrastructure	World Bank - World Development Indicators

Source: authors

Digitalization readiness in CEE countries

The data for the group of central and southeast Europe countries for the RFTI are available for period 2008-2019 (158 countries) and the rank for the countries is available for 2021 and 2022 (166 countries). The performance of the analysed central and southeast European countries expressed by the RFTI are given in the following Table. We have aligned countries based on their RFTI score for years 2008-2019. As seen, the most technologically and digitally developed countries are Czechia, Hungary, Estonia, Poland and Slovenia. Otherwise, the low scores have Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia and Montenegro.

Table 3: The ranking of the central and southeast European countries based on their RFTI 2008 – 2019 (the overall world position given in parenthesis)

Country / Year	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Bulgaria	11 (43)	11 (44)	11 (43)	11 (41)	9 (39)	11 (42)	11 (43)	11 (43)	11 (42)	10 (42)	12 (46)	12 (51)
Czechia	1 (26)	1 (26)	2 (28)	1 (27)	2 (28)	1 (27)	1 (30)	1 (30)	2 (30)	1 (26)	1 (25)	1 (26)
Estonia	4 (30)	6 (35)	6 (33)	5 (31)	3 (31)	3 (31)	3 (32)	3 (32)	4 (33)	5 (33)	3 (29)	3 (29)
Hungary	3 (28)	2 (28)	1 (26)	3 (29)	1 (27)	2 (29)	2 (31)	9 (39)	6 (35)	4 (32)	5 (34)	6 (37)
Latvia	5 (32)	4 (30)	3 (29)	2 (28)	7 (35)	7 (36)	7 (36)	8 (38)	8 (39)	6 (36)	7 (38)	9 (40)
Lithuania	8 (38)	5 (32)	10 (42)	8 (37)	11 (43)	8 (37)	4 (33)	5 (34)	5 (34)	8 (39)	8 (39)	8 (39)
Poland	7 (37)	9 (39)	8 (37)	9 (38)	4 (32)	10 (39)	10 (40)	2 (31)	1 (27)	2 (29)	2 (28)	2 (28)
Romania	12 (44)	10 (42)	4 (31)	6 (33)	6 (34)	6 (35)	5 (34)	6 (36)	9 (40)	11 (43)	10 (42)	10 (45)
Slovakia	6 (35)	7 (37)	7 (35)	7 (35)	8 (36)	5 (34)	9 (38)	10 (42)	10 (41)	7 (38)	6 (35)	5 (36)
Slovenia	2 (27)	3 (29)	5 (32)	4 (30)	5 (33)	4 (33)	6 (35)	4 (33)	3 (31)	3 (30)	4 (32)	4 (33)
Albania	17 (103)	17 (95)	17 (98)	17 (79)	17 (81)	17 (81)	17 (82)	17 (87)	17 (89)	17 (86)	17 (85)	17 (85)
Bosnia and Herzegovina	16 (71)	16 (71)	16 (73)	16 (69)	15 (68)	15 (68)	16 (77)	15 (69)	14 (76)	16 (72)	16 (79)	16 (80)
Croatia	10 (42)	12 (45)	12 (45)	12 (44)	12 (44)	12 (48)	12 (47)	12 (47)	12 (48)	12 (45)	11 (43)	13 (52)
Greece	9 (40)	8 (38)	9 (38)	10 (39)	10 (40)	9 (38)	8 (37)	7 (37)	7 (38)	9 (40)	9 (40)	7 (38)
Montenegro	14 (60)	15 (64)	15 (65)	15 (66)	16 (73)	16 (73)	15 (68)	16 (74)	16 (79)	14 (68)	15 (73)	14 (70)

North Macedonia	15 (61)	13 (55)	13 (54)	14 (52)	14 (59)	14 (63)	14 (67)	14 (68)	15 (77)	15 (71)	14 (67)	15 (73)
Serbia	13 (56)	14 (56)	14 (63)	13 (51)	13 (51)	13 (51)	13 (54)	13 (51)	13 (53)	13 (48)	13 (51)	11 (47)

Source: authors, UNCTADstat

To continue with the ranking, the position of countries for 2021 and 2022 is directly calculated by UNCTAD. The overall position across included countries as well as the ranking within the central and southeast countries is shown in Table 4. The best score for the latest reported year was achieved by Poland is 27th in the worldwide rank of countries (from 166 assessed and included in the RFTI). The second is Slovenia and the third is Estonia. The worst score and ranking have Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina and North Macedonia. The situation at the bottom of the ranking as well as for top central and southeast Europe countries is very similar to period 2008-2019 that we have calculated. Only noticeable change is in position of Czechia that was most of the time leader of the digitalization, innovation and digitalization, but has dropped by 3 places to position 4 within the central and southeast Europe countries

Table 4: The ranking of the central and southeast European countries based on their RFTI 2021 – 2022 (the overall world position given in parenthesis)

Country / Year	2021	2022
Bulgaria	12 (51)	10 (43)
Czechia	1 (26)	4 (30)
Estonia	3 (29)	3 (29)
Hungary	6 (37)	5 (36)
Latvia	9 (40)	6 (38)
Lithuania	8 (39)	8 (41)
Poland	2 (28)	1 (27)
Romania	10 (45)	12 (45)
Slovakia	5 (36)	7 (39)
Slovenia	4 (33)	2 (28)
Albania	17 (85)	17 (88)
Bosnia and Herzegovina	16 (80)	16 (76)
Croatia	13 (52)	9 (42)
Greece	7 (38)	11 (44)
Montenegro	14 (70)	14 (59)
North Macedonia	15 (73)	15 (74)
Serbia	11 (47)	13 (50)

Source: authors; UNCTAD, 2021; UNCTAD, 2023

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